

3D-BioInfo

ELIXIR Community in Structural Bioinformatics

ELIXIR Italy All Hands Meeting
November 27th-28th, 2023

3D-BioInfo

Executive Committee

Christine Orengo *UK*, **Sameer Velankar** *EBI*, **Shoshana Wodak** *Belgium*, **Vincent Zoete** *Switzerland*,
Bohdan Schneider *Czech Republic*, **Lynne Regan** *UK*

Steering Committee

Sweden: Arne Elofsson, **Finland:** Tiina Salminen, Rik Wierenga **France:** Pierre Tuffery, **Germany:** Matthias Rarey,
Italy: Manuela Helmer-Citterich, **Netherlands:** Anton, Feenstra, **Portugal:** Irina Moreira, **Spain:** Adam Hospital,
Gonzalo Parra **Israel:** Emmanuel Levy, **Greece:** Evangelica Chrysina

INSTRUCT: Jon Agirre, *UK*, Alexandre Bonvin, *Netherlands*

3D-BioInfo contact list includes >200 members

We hold **monthly zoom calls**, **bimonthly webinars** and organize an annual AGM and Activity workshops

Major Activities for the 3D-BioInfo Community

Activity 1

Analysing and predicting structures and structural annotations (eg predicted functional sites, variant impacts)

Activity 2

Analysing and predicting protein complexes; and conformational landscape of proteins

Activity 3

Analysing and predicting protein – ligand interactions

Activity 4

Analysing and predicting protein-nucleic acid interactions

Activity 5

Structure based protein design and engineering

Major Activities for the 3D-BioInfo Community

Activity 1 To develop the infrastructure for FAIR structural and functional annotations

Sameer Velankar, PDBe, EBI

PDBe-KB
3D-Beacons

PDBe Knowledge Base

30 partner groups from 10 nodes

PDBe-KB Consortium partners provide annotation in the PDB to define the biological context of structural data

PDBe Knowledge Base

30 partner groups
From 10 nodes

PDBe-KB partner annotations:

- Domain annotations
- Rfam classifications
- Ligand-binding sites
- Covalent binders
- Drug-binding pockets
- Variants and their effects
- Sequence conservation
- Macromolecular interaction interfaces
- Post-translational modifications
- Backbone flexibility and intrinsic disorder
- Residue accessibility and depth

pdbe-kb.org

SWITZERLAND

HU

MobiDB: a database of protein disorder and mobility annotations

1

CROATIA

MetalPDB collects and allows easy access to the knowledge on metal sites in biological macromolecules, starting from the structural information contained in the Protein Data Bank

1

BOSNIA AND
HERZEGOVINA

ITALY

Adriatic Sea

MO

AKID is a Deep Neural Network-based method that identifies kinase-specific phosphorylation events at single-kinase level in any given Eukaryotic proteome

1

PDBe-KB consortium. PDBe-KB: a community-driven resource for structural and functional annotations. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2020 Jan 8;48(D1):D344-D353

PDBe-KB consortium. PDBe-KB: collaboratively defining the biological context of structural data. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2022 Jan 7;50(D1):D534-D542

3D-Beacons Network

Unified programmatic access to experimentally determined and predicted structure models.

Provides API endpoints keyed on UniProt accessions

Data providers include: AlphaFold DB, PDBe, Swiss-Model, ModelArchive, SASBDB, PED, AlphaFill and more

Supports sequence-based search

3D-Beacons is an open collaborations between providers of macromolecular structure models

Major Activities for the 3D-BioInfo Community

Activity 2

Analysing and predicting protein complexes; characterizing the conformational landscape of proteins

Shoshana Wodak, VIB-VUB, Belgium

CAPRI organiser

ELIXIR Implementation Plan

- Evaluated tools and resources for scoring protein-protein complexes
- Benchmark dataset of physiological and non-physiological homodimers from the PDB
- Paper on benchmarking tools for scoring protein interfaces (Wiley-Proteomics)

ELIXIR Implementation Study

Building on PDBe to chart the conformational landscape of native proteins

- Evaluated tools for sequence and structure alignments and clustering
- Benchmark datasets of conformational ensembles of PDB structures
- FAIR workflows of tools for the prediction of protein ensembles
- GAP analysis (3D-Bioinfo/IDP/Proteomics)

Examples from the **Benchmark dataset** of protein conformational ensembles.

Clusters of conformations of ATPase (80% seq-id) identified by a K-means clustering in the eigenspace of the protein.

Monthly calls - Groups regularly involved from 10 nodes and US

23 expert groups:
from 10 Elixir
nodes, and 2
external expert
groups

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Major Activities for the 3D-BioInfo Community

Activity 3 Analysing and predicting protein – ligand interactions

Vincent Zoete, SIB LICR, Switzerland

Objective:

Create a large-scale benchmark of characterized ligand-biomacromolecule complexes:

Calculate **physico-chemical properties** of ligands and biomacromolecules

Generate relevant **conformations of the ligands**

Provide **binding free energy**, where possible

Provide list of **known non-binders**

Groups from 8 nodes involved

PDB Europe - UK
S. Velankar, L. Pravda

Thornton's Group – UK
J. Thornton, J. Tyzack

Tuffery's Group – France
P. Tuffery

Grudinin's Group – France
S. Grudinin, M. Kadukova

Chacon's Group – Spain
P. Chacon

PDB-Redo - NL
A. Perrakis, R. Joosten

Rarey's Group – Germany
M. Rarey, K. Stierand

Dejeagere/Stote's Group - France
A. Dejeagere / R. Stote

Svobodova's Group – Czech R.
R. Svobodova

SwissModel - Switzerland
T. Schwede, G. Tauriello, X. Robin,
L. Alexander

SIB Molecular Modelling – Switzer.
V. Zoete, A. Prunotto, U. Röhrig, F.
Tessaro, A. Daina

Activity 3 training workshop in 2024

5-days on-site teaching on structure-based computer-aided drug design in Spring 2024

Major Activities for the 3D-BioInfo Community

Activity 4 Analysing and predicting protein-nucleic acid interactions

Bohdan Schneider
Institute of Biotechnology of the Czech
Academy of Sciences, CZ

Objectives

- Improve and integrate tools to **build, refine, & validate** NA 3D models
 - collaboration with *Instruct-ERIC*, *PDB-dev*
- Interoperability between data and exchange protocols:
 - **FAIR principles based on mmCIF dictionary**

NA-VAL Working Group:

Expert groups from 4 ELIXIR nodes and US to evaluate NA geometry

UK Abhik Mukhopadhyay
UK Paul Emsley
UK Garib Murshudov
UK Gary Parkinson
UK Ian Bruno
UK Paul Emsley
EMBL Sameer Velankar

NL Robbie P. Joosten

PL Mariusz Jaskolski

CZ Jiří Černý

CZ Bohdan Schneider

US Martin Egli
US Helen M. Berman
US Catherine L. Lawson
US Nigel W. Moriarty
US Jane S. Richardson
US Stephen K. Burley
US David A. Case
US Rhiju Das
US Martin Egli
US Zukang Feng
US Oleg V. Sobolev
US Brinda Vallat
US Evan Worden
US Evan Worden

Benchmarking of programs assigning base pair classes

- Benchmarking of tools that calculate base pairing geometries and assign base pairs
- The goal is to select 1-2 programs or algorithms
- New mmCIF category will be developed to capture all features of the pairing

Berman HM, Lawson CL, Schneider B. Developing Community Resources for Nucleic Acid Structures. *Life (Basel)*. 2022 Apr 6;12(4):540.

Major Activities for the 3D-BioInfo Community

Activity 5 Structure based protein design and engineering

Lynne Regan,
University of Edinburgh, UK

4 nodes involved: UK, Belgium, Denmark, Finland

Protein Design Database

Ongoing Activities

1) A comprehensive database of protein designs

Working with **BioStudies** to refine the submission process and then it will be open for community submission

2) Collection of tools for protein engineering and design.

Identify useful programmes. Accessibility and ease of use for non-experts are key.

3) Identify and collect high quality benchmark datasets.

FEBS Workshops on Protein Engineering, joint with 3D-BioInfo held in Finland 2022, Croatia 2023

FEBS 2023
ADVANCED COURSE

Community Outreach

5 AGMs – 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023

Bimonthly webinar series now joint with 3D-SIG in ISCB to promote dissemination

3D-BioInfo Workshop at ELIXIR All Hands 2019

Activity 2 Workshop at ELIXIR All hands 2021

Activity 1 Workshop at ELIXIR All Hands 2023

Workflows in **TESS** on protein structure prediction

Interactions with other communities

Intercommunity 'gap analysis' between:

IDP, 3D-Bioinfo and Proteomics Communities

Establish:

links between the tools and databases

standard terminology to describe and investigate proteins

(different levels of disorder, different structural features, different types of experimental data, etc).

Lead is Wim Vranken of the IDP community.

Working towards a white paper with results of the gap analysis, subscribed by the three communities,

Interactions with other communities

Machine Learning Community:

DOME initiative

Research Data Management Community:

3D-BioInfo representative on the steering committee

IDP and Proteomics community

Intercommunity GAP analysis (3D-BioInfo/IDP/Proteomics) ongoing

Interactions with Platforms

Data - Research Data Management Kit

Interoperability - interaction with Bioschemas

Tools - bio.tools tagging relevant tools

Training - TESS workflows

The white paper of the 3D-Bioinfo Community

Orengo C, Velankar S, Wodak S, Zoete V, Bonvin AMJJ, Elofsson A, Feenstra KA, Gerloff DL, Hamelryck T, Hancock JM, Helmer-Citterich M, Hospital A, Orozco M, Perrakis A, Rarey M, Soares C, Sussman JL, Thornton JM, Tuffery P, Tusnady G, Wierenga R, Salminen T, Schneider B. A community proposal to integrate structural bioinformatics activities in ELIXIR (3D-Bioinfo Community). F1000Res. 2020 Apr 22;9:ELIXIR-278.

With acknowledgments to the 3D-Bioinfo Community

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collaborations between members of the 3D-Bioinfo Italian community

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Paiardini A. Protein Structure Prediction in Drug Discovery. *Biomolecules*. 2023 Aug 17;13(8):1258.

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3D-BioInfo

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Website:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1iZjQzhw-MLrdC88fE6zIDtAh7igxCplv>

Tools/resources catalogue:

<https://forms.gle/ZUQSJ3NuPvm6hxb48>

Bio.Tools 3D-BioInfo Collections

